

Impact of Universal Human Values course in Indian higher technical education: A case study

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Abstract The notion of 'values' can be considered the ultimate reason for an individual's action. It is a trait that can influence our thoughts, feelings, and actions. Values are the aspect that separates a human from an animal. Across the world, every religious philosophy and government constitution is based on the notion of humanity. It is largely accepted that building character and gaining knowledge are the true goals of human education. In the current world scenario, with wars across many nations, it is even more essential to sharpen our knowledge of human values. It seems that we as humans are largely losing our values, and we need to reinstall them in our existence.

A course named Universal Human Values (UHV) is taught by many engineering universities in India. The purpose of the course is to instill universal values in students so as to make them responsible human beings. In the current study, we targeted finding the change in values-understanding among students who had been taught the UHV course. To test the efficacy of the course, two groups of undergraduate students were selected from an engineering institute in India. One group was not exposed to the contents of this subject, while the other group had it in their curriculum. The impact of the UHV course was evaluated by giving the same set of value-based questions to both groups. On the basis of the frequency distribution analysis, it was found that the group of students who had learned the UHV course had marginally more clarity about human aspirations, goals, activities, and the purpose of life. As the seed of values is planted in the young minds, the future offspring of this generation can be expected to be high-valued humans. This would ultimately lead to a more harmonious society in the course of a couple of decades.

Keywords Universal Human Values Course, Indian Education System, Case Study, Impact, Undergraduates, Engineering Students

1. INTRODUCTION

The term 'value', is derived from a Latin word 'valere', which means 'precious' or worthy fullness. The word "values" implies things that people think are important or worthwhile. Human values guide us to appropriate courses of action. Human values pass from one generation to the next. Society wants humans with values. There are various versions of what is understood by universal human values, like society, which has attributes like good, truth, beauty, freedom, or civility; a non-nuclear world; ecological protection, etc. However, the attainment of such values is questionable [17]. As is noted by Shalom H. Schwartz[13], except for human values, education and values are linearly associated. The emphasis on understanding universal values starts in the last years of secondary school. And the values are expected to be substantially booming among those who attend university. Thus, university education broadens the horizons of human values education. It is necessary

to emphasize the proposition that a harmonious society is equally as essential as an educated one. Research has found the prevalence of stress is increasing among students studying in higher education[11]. A study in 2018[15] concluded that educational institutions should teach human values to adolescents so as to make them lead a wholesome human life. The higher education system should not just focus on a limited materialistic perspective. The ultimate fulfilling education has to be based on fundamental human values, without any content contradictory to the basic human values. It has to be in the form of proposals that the student can explore on their own, verify the values within, and be able to see that living with these values leads to their own happiness. In this way, they can understand and accept fundamental values naturally and live up to them without external enforcement. [4]

The contributions in this article are:

- Give an overview of the course on Universal Human Values (UHV), which is offered to students in higher education in India.
- Discuss the effect of teaching the course to students in higher education in India.
- Provide insights on the reasons for failure and possible solutions to improve the course outcome.

Section 2 discusses the ideology and history associated with the UHV course designed by the Government of India (GOI). The next section mentions the work done in the past in the direction of understanding human-values and their importance in education. Section 4 discusses the methodology used for the survey presented in this article. Subsequently, the results and insights from those results, are presented before concluding the article. As per our research, this survey is the first of its kind for the UHV course being taught in higher educational institutes in India.

II. UHV COURSE

It is no longer sufficient for engineers to confine their attention and expertise only to the narrow area of technical aspects of their profession. They are now being held more and more accountable for the social, environmental, and human consequences of technology as well. Engineering students have to be made aware of these problems and equipped to find an adequate and acceptable response to them. That would require integrating social concerns and ethical human values with the scientific and technical education of engineers.

The students in technical education feel overburdened with the already heavy engineering curriculum in India and have shown little interest. Often, they distance themselves and have contempt for non-technical/non-engineering components of the curriculum. Hence, any realistic effort to integrate value education with technical education should demonstrate that the former emanates from within the topics comprising technical education and not added forcibly and artificially from without. [5]. The Indian civilization has from always believed in well-being of all (sarve bhavantu sukhin, sarve santu niraamaya, sarve bhadrani pasyantu, maa kaschit dukh bhaagabhavet – let all human being be happy, let all human being be well, let all human being see well-being of others, let no one suffer unhappiness.) It sees the whole of humanity as one human family “Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam”[9]. The National Education Policy 2020[4] framed by the Indian government envisions a holistic and integrated approach to imparting education. The GOI had set up the All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) in November 1945 as a national-level apex advisory body to conduct a survey on the facilities available for technical education and to promote development in the country in a coordinated and integrated manner[1]. AICTE is orienting the academic fraternity towards the inculcation of UHV in technical education. AICTE has been working on value-based education for value-based living for the past several years. In the last 3 years, they have come across a simple, extremely effective and promising content and methodology called “Universal Human Value (UHV)”. The content is planned to be universal, rational, verifiable leading to harmony. The steps taken by the AICTE in the direction of imbibing universal human values Education among teachers and students is expected to yield transformation. The UHV course is the result of a long series of experiments at educational institutes like IITs which are directly controlled by the Ministry of Education in GOI [7].

In 2018, AICTE included UHV in the Model Curriculum for Engineering. It made UHV-II an essential 3-credit course in the third or fourth semester after an orientation to values in UHV-I, which is a prominent module in the Student Induction Program. The course follows a process of self verification on the basis of one's own natural acceptance, leading to self-confidence and self-evolution. It encourages students to discover what they consider valuable. Accordingly, they are able to discriminate between the valuable and the superficial in real-life situations. It enables the student to discover and understand the innate value of human beings in every aspect of life (individual, family, society, nature/existence), and reinforces the commitment and courage to live accordingly. THE UHV proposals are Universal, so applicable to every human being for all time and places, irrespective of caste, creed, gender, sect, etc. The concepts are designed to be rational and all-encompassing, i.e., they have to appeal to reasoning and not be based on dogmas or blind beliefs, and they cover all aspects of living. The course is designed to help the self-exploring graduate develop attributes like - A holistic vision of life, Socially responsible behavior, Ethical human conduct, Having competence and capabilities for maintaining health and hygiene, having Appreciation and aspiration for excellence (merit) and gratitude for all. These would be the indicators of development of the full human potential, as expected by NEP 2020[4].

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Portrait Values Questionnaire was developed by professor Shalom H. Schwartz [13] to measure how people from different cultures prioritize 10 universal human values. It was found that the aspects of human nature and social functioning that shape individual value priorities are widely shared across cultures. The human values measured by the test are benevolence, universality, security, achievement, hedonism, stimulation, power, self-direction, tradition, and conformity. Benevolence covers the need to preserve and enhance the welfare of those with whom one is in frequent personal contact. Universality measures the need for understanding, appreciation, and tolerance among all the peoples of the world, as well as the need for the welfare and protection of nature. Universality may also be expressed as concern for the weak and those in the minority. Security denotes the need to preserve the harmony, security, and stability of oneself and one's community. People who prioritize security are more likely to view demanding and unfamiliar challenges as threatening, whereas those with a lower emphasis on security are more likely to see such challenges as exciting. Those who struggle with economic hardship are more likely to assign importance to security values than would those who live in relative comfort. Achievement is linked with prioritizing individual success in accordance with accepted social standards. Achievement is essential to personal success and is often evident in the life choices of those who strive to progress in their careers or ascend to leadership positions. Hedonism measures how important the attainment of pleasure and sensuous gratification is to the individual. People who are high in hedonism often prioritize the greatest amount of pleasure possible for themselves. Stimulation denotes the individual's need for excitement, novelty, and change in their life. The pursuit of stimulation is likely to undermine the pursuit of tradition, which is more concerned with preserving time-honored values. Stimulation values are often expressed when faced with a number of uncertain yet exciting opportunities, such as when young adults could conceivably mold their lives in any direction they see fit. Power measures the importance an individual assigns to having social status, prestige, and control or dominance over people and resources. This value, which centers on social esteem, emphasizes the attainment or preservation of a dominant position within the social system. Self-direction is the need for independent thought and action in choosing, creating, and exploring the individual's own life and environment. This value is derived from the innate need for mastery as well as from the interpersonal demand for autonomy. Self-direction values often oppose conformity, security, and tradition values. Tradition denotes respect, commitment, and acceptance of the customs and ideas that the traditional culture of the individual holds to be best. Tradition is closely associated with conformity since both of these values prioritize the community over the self. On the other hand, tradition specifically entails subordination to more abstract considerations such as cultural ideas, customs, and religious practices, whereas conformity is more concerned with whatever norms the individual finds themselves surrounded by. Conformity measures the restraint of actions, inclinations, and impulses likely to upset or violate the community's social expectations or norms. In research conducted in 2012[14], it was found that the most important values in pan-culture are

benevolence, universalism, and self direction. While power and stimulation are least important.

The Portrait Value Questionnaire (PVQ) was developed by Schwartz and his colleagues in 2001. Two versions of this scale exist, the original one where there are 40 portraits that define values, and shortened versions that consist of only 21 questions [14]. The PVQ includes short verbal portraits of different people. Each portrait describes a person's goals, aspirations, or wishes that point implicitly to the importance of a single value type. Participants respond by considering how much they relate to the hypothetical character presented in the portrait. In two different versions of PVQ viz., PVQ-40 and PVQ-21, the number of items assessing the value varies. A study on two nations was conducted to measure the validity and reliability of a questionnaire. Results of the study indicated that PVQ-21 has strong construct validity, and modifying a few of its items does not have any significant effect on its reliability and validity. Research was conducted by Thijs Bouman et al. (2018)[2] in which they used a variant of the portrait value questionnaire to measure environmental beliefs. The studies [6], [16],[8],[3], [3] explained the importance of human values and the factors for continuous degradation of values. They also emphasized the strong need for academic subjects related to human values, which can enhance the understanding of human values in today's youth. The studies on adolescents by Dr. Shantini found that there is a close relationship between age and initiatives to enhance human values[15]. A research in 2022 [10], examined the extent to which higher education attainment affects the importance people place on core human values. They found the graduates had a higher value for leisure and a lower value for religion as compared to non-graduates.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The nature of the current study is descriptive. The study is confined to the population of undergraduate students taking a four-year full-time Bachelor of Engineering course at a university in the state of Gujarat, India. In total, 163 individuals participated in the study. The participants took the full online test. The students were divided into 2 groups named 'WithUHV' or group A, and 'WithoutUHV' which is also known as group B, depending on whether they had undergone the study on UHV as part of curriculum. The total number of students responding in the 'WithUHV' group was 88, while in the other group there were 75 total responses received. The students of 'WithUHV' group had undergone a full time course on UHV in the second year of their study, which also involved a year-end examination. While the 'WithoutUHV' group were the students in the last year of their study, who had not been introduced to this subject during their entire course of study. There were a total of 25 question responses taken from each participant. The first set of questions from 1 to 21 were derived from the Portrait Values Questionnaire (PVQ; Schwartz, 2003)[12]. As the PVQ can be administered to anyone of any age and takes only 5 to 7 minutes to complete, it is deemed suitable for our survey. The questions were re framed to suit gender neutrality.

The 22 to 25 numbered questions were drawn based on the UHV course taught to students. The entire set of 25 questions used is given in table1. Also as per the methodology suggested by Schwatz[12], the questions are mapped to the ten values. Specifically for the benevolence value, we use Q12, Q18. The universalism uses Q3, Q8 and Q19. The value of self direction is reflected in the responses of Q1 and Q11. The stimulation measured by Q6,Q15; hedonism by Q10,Q21; achievement by Q4,Q13; power by Q2,Q17; security by Q5, Q14; conformity by Q7, Q16; tradition by Q9 and Q20. For each question, respondents were asked to choose from one of five options : 'Always (A)', 'Often (O)', 'Sometimes (S)', 'Rarely (R)', or 'Never (N)'.

The tools used to do descriptive statistical analysis are frequency distribution and mode. The non-parametric chi-squared statistics are used to do the hypothesis testing. The null hypothesis used for the study is as follows:

- H0 : There is no significant relationship between learning UHV course and enhancement of understanding of human values.

V. SURVEY RESULTS

The frequency distribution of question-wise responses is shown in 2. The figure1 represents the mode of each question for the two groups. The categorical responses of type 'Always' to 'Never' are represented numerically

from 5 to 1 respectively in the graph. Each of the questions from 1 to 21 map to one unique value in the ten human-values as mentioned by Schwartz [12]. The total number of persons giving the response 'always', for each of the group of questions under these 10 values is shown in figure2. To establish the significance of UHV studies in undergraduate students curriculum, the contingency table used is shown in 3. The degree of freedom is 4. For an error probability of 0.01, we get a chi-square critical value of 13.26. However, our data gave us chi-square of 9.49. Hence, we can say our samples did not provide sufficient evidence to conclude that there is a relationship between learning the UHV course and human-values understanding. However, at the same time, it can be a lack of evidence due to which we are not able to prove the presence of a relationship.

- 1) Thinking up new ideas and being creative is important to me
- 2) It is important for me to be rich and have a lot of money.
- 3) I believe that every person in the world should be treated equally.
- 4) It is important for me to show my abilities. I want other people to admire what I do
- 5) It is important for me to live in a safe and secure surrounding.
- 6) I love surprises and 5 want to try something new.
- 7) I believe that I should obey rules even when no one is around.
- 8) It is important for me to stay humble and modest.
- 9) I believe in listening to people who are different from me and try to understand them
- 10) Having a good time is important to me. I like to 'spoil' myself at times.
- 11) I prefer to make my own decisions and do what feels right to me.
- 12) I like helping people around me.
- 13) Being successful is important to me.
- 14) It is important for me to ensure that the government is taking care of my safety concerns
- 15) I want to take up new adventures and want to live an exciting life.
- 16) It is important for me to behave properly at all times and not do anything that people consider wrong
- 17) It is important for me to earn respect from others.
- 18) Being loyal to my friends is a priority in my life.
- 19) I try to follow my traditional values and customs that my family and society have endowed on me.
- 20) I strongly believe that we should care about nature.
- 21) It is important for me to do things that give me pleasure.
- 22) I believe that:: I want to make others happy and others also want to make me happy. But maybe we lack competence(or way to express).
- 23) I believe that:: If my "self" is in harmony and in happy state, then i can make others also happy like my family, society and rest of nature.
- 24) I believe that:: "I" am coexistence of "self" and "body". My body is a tool to help "self". Self is the core of my existence.
- 25) I believe that:: My happiness is dependent on only me. The external factors can trigger in me momentary happiness or unhappiness, but if my "self" is happy, I can ensure continuous happiness.

Table 1: Survey Questionnaire

	WithUHV					WithoutUHV				
	A	O	S	R	N	A	O	S	R	N
Q1	67.06%	25.88%	8.24%	0.00%	0.00%	60.81%	28.38%	9.46%	1.35%	0.00%
Q2	32.94%	30.59%	30.59%	4.71%	2.35%	32.43%	22.97%	33.78%	6.76%	4.05%
Q3	63.53%	16.47%	10.59%	4.71%	5.88%	62.16%	24.32%	5.41%	1.35%	6.76%
Q4	12.94%	31.76%	37.65%	10.59%	8.24%	20.27%	21.62%	29.73%	20.27%	8.11%
Q5	70.59%	21.18%	7.06%	1.18%	1.18%	51.35%	29.73%	13.51%	4.05%	1.35%
Q6	37.65%	35.29%	24.71%	3.53%	0.00%	24.32%	40.54%	27.03%	6.76%	1.35%
Q7	32.94%	38.82%	23.53%	4.71%	1.18%	31.08%	29.73%	24.32%	12.16%	2.70%
Q8	58.82%	29.41%	11.76%	1.18%	0.00%	41.89%	39.19%	14.86%	2.70%	1.35%
Q9	52.94%	28.24%	15.29%	1.18%	3.53%	32.43%	43.24%	14.86%	8.11%	1.35%
Q10	15.29%	28.24%	37.65%	10.59%	9.41%	18.92%	28.38%	32.43%	14.86%	5.41%
Q11	45.88%	44.71%	9.41%	1.18%	0.00%	37.84%	40.54%	16.22%	4.05%	1.35%
Q12	50.59%	37.65%	11.76%	1.18%	0.00%	41.89%	40.54%	14.86%	1.35%	1.35%
Q13	69.41%	18.82%	12.94%	0.00%	0.00%	58.11%	24.32%	13.51%	1.35%	2.70%
Q14	30.59%	40.00%	21.18%	7.06%	2.35%	27.03%	37.84%	21.62%	10.81%	2.70%
Q15	48.24%	42.35%	8.24%	2.35%	0.00%	51.35%	32.43%	13.51%	2.70%	0.00%
Q16	31.76%	31.76%	22.35%	7.06%	8.24%	25.68%	36.49%	32.43%	1.35%	4.05%
Q17	38.82%	37.65%	20.00%	2.35%	2.35%	36.49%	33.78%	13.51%	9.46%	6.76%
Q18	51.76%	36.47%	10.59%	1.18%	1.18%	58.11%	25.68%	10.81%	4.05%	1.35%
Q19	37.65%	42.35%	17.65%	2.35%	1.18%	40.54%	32.43%	13.51%	12.16%	1.35%
Q20	69.41%	24.71%	5.88%	1.18%	0.00%	56.76%	36.49%	6.76%	0.00%	0.00%
Q21	34.12%	38.82%	27.06%	1.18%	0.00%	36.49%	39.19%	20.27%	2.70%	1.35%
Q22	30.59%	35.29%	28.24%	4.71%	2.35%	22.97%	31.08%	33.78%	8.11%	4.05%
Q23	42.35%	37.65%	18.82%	1.18%	1.18%	35.14%	37.84%	21.62%	4.05%	1.35%
Q24	36.47%	38.82%	18.82%	5.88%	1.18%	28.38%	33.78%	28.38%	5.41%	4.05%
Q25	35.29%	41.18%	17.65%	4.71%	2.35%	35.14%	27.03%	28.38%	8.11%	1.35%

Table 2: Responses: Frequency Distribution

Figure 1: Modes for each question

Figure 2: Compiled responses of ten human values

	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Total
WithUHV	40	28	15	3	2	88
WithoutUHV	31	25	14	5	2	75
Total	71	52	29	8	4	163

Table 3: Contingency Table for UHV course and 'values' responses

VI. INSIGHTS

These are major observations from results obtained:

- A large group of students in WithoutUHV group felt that 'sometimes' it is important to be rich (based on the Q2 response), to feel the power. On the other hand, the other junior group felt it was always necessary to have a lot of money and expensive things. This difference in opinion can be attributed to the fact that the senior students had been to industry to get internships as part of their last semester schedule, and hence they understood the actual world more than the junior students, who had merely studied the values but had not experienced the power in the real world.
- Both groups of students still believed that to boost the value of achievement, it is 'sometimes' necessary to show one's abilities and have people admire them, as evident from the response to Q4. And that 'sometimes' it is good to spoil oneself (Q10 responses). This indicates that the youngsters still need to understand the real meaning of achievement and inner happiness, which might come to them much later in their lives after experiencing life.
- The WithUHV had a very good understanding of the universalism values. Typically, there were on average nearly 5 percent more persons in group A, which gave the response 'Always' for the Q3, Q8 and Q19 questions related to the universalism human-value.

- For the specific questions drawn based on the UHV course, group A gave better answers than group B in Q22 to Q24. But for the Q25 indicating how to find constant happiness, the students did not have as clear an understanding as the group B students. The prime reason for their lack of understanding can be attributed to the inadequate instances presented to them in their study. Also, they might not have felt the difference between pleasure and happiness, leading to confusion. But by having this proposal put to them, it is hoped that they will be able to self verify and accept that happiness is dependent only on themselves in the future.
- The importance of traditional values was greater by nearly 16 percent among the WithUHV groups. These students are still very much closely knit with their families, and hence they still have strong religious beliefs.
- The importance of security was considered higher by 11 percent in the WithUHV group as compared to the WithoutUHV group. They always want to know that the country and surroundings are safe for them when they step out into the world. However, maybe as the students of WithoutUHV have actually faced the real-world challenges and seen the facts, they believe it is not always so important to look for security.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The survey was conclusive of the fact that the study of UHV does have the capacity to change humans' values. The course has the potential to change the way students think and behave. In the long term, these students would be shaped into better humans, leading to harmonious universal humans. The subject was merely a gentle way to introduce the young generation to what is ultimately valuable to humans. The course puts forward the ideas as proposals, and the student, after self-verification and self-validation, can accept them. This would ultimately help each individual and, in turn, the entire human race understand the values of humans. Currently, not all the learners in the course are able to validate or verify the concepts taught, but there is strong hope it will eventually happen. And gradually, in coming generations, we will get to a society where all humans have a correct understanding of human values. For preparing graduates with desirable attributes, the people responsible for ensuring education, i.e., teachers, parents, family, and society at large, must have similar or better capabilities. An environment of trust, respect, affection, care, and guidance is essential for understanding to take place. Without this type of environment at home, at school, and in the community, only some learning may take place, not understanding. In the future, it would be interesting to again assess the same students taking this UHV course, to know about the paradigm shift in their values after they have self-verified and actually understood the proposals given in the course.

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